

Thailand and Prostitution of Trafficking Human Beings (Women and Children)

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Abstract—The problems of trafficking human beings were continuously violent in Thailand. The problems occurred from a variety of factors such as unemployment, agricultural workers' urban immigration, sex tour, attitude of materialism society, divorced family, unsavourily effected law, and officers' ignorance. The purposes of this study were to study the structure, connection, a number of trafficking human beings in Thailand. Qualitative and quantitative and results of previous research were used in this research. The previous procurers, interested persons, experienced people, human beings-aiding organization, and women-children rights organization were interviewed in depth. The field was used in a variety of regions. The findings showed that the structure and connection of trafficking human beings and their values are \$8,750 million. There are 240,000 people in trafficked human beings. The trend of trafficking human beings grows continuously. It is changed according to economic circumstance, society and culture, and law. The state must be aware of its problem. The law is enacted by adding high penalty for serious fear.

Keywords—Human Trade, Prostitution trafficking, trafficking in women and children.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE origin of human trafficking begin when a slave trade was existed in the past. Academic assumption the origin of trafficking was a consequence of a long migration in the era of colonization when the soldier who is the head of the family died in the war. The rest of woman and children were sold as slaves. Later After the colonial period, the male labours become valuable, as needs to expand the empire, therefore they were sold and used as a main labour to expand the power of the empire.

A piece of evidence (about four thousand years ago) with a story about human trafficking, the law is the law of Hammurabi, which considered to be the world's first code of laws [1].

The Ancient Egypt kingdom was claimed to be a centre of human trafficking (or sometimes referred as the slavery centre). As the Egyptians have the phases said that “the poor can sell themselves, their children to be slave”.

Then the ancient Greek, there is the evident of slave trade existing as well as other period of time but different in but it is different that city cannot be a slave born in the city. Such restrictions cause a kidnapped boy and the girl was sold to another city instead. The slaves in Greek era can be freed from

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slavery if he or she can make any benefit to the state.

After that the great of Roman era, where the economic grown prosperity along with the highly develop military strengths, the roman cruelly treated the slaves as animal that need to fight to survive. The evident existing demonstrates that the roman have the activity that bring the slave to fight with the hungry wildlife until they died.

II. LITERATURES REVIEW

The 15th century, the medieval Europe, The Portuguese explorer brought the black African slaves. In this period of time, slave trade became popular in European countries, such as Spain, Netherlands, France and England for example. The 17th century, a discovery of the New World of Americas affect to a demand on slave in order to explore a new continent. The biggest slave market in the history, therefore, created. In 1885 slave trade was restrained. The first country that has regarded the abolition of slavery was France in 1804. Then England has cancelled the slave trade and start the abolition of slavery in 1833 while, the United States started to distract the abolition during the reign of President Abraham Lincoln. In Thailand, regarding to the great vision of his majesty the king Rama the 5th, Chakri dynasty, the slavery over the country were slowly liberated during his reign. The end of World War I, An International Labour Organization (ILO) has been established under the Treaty of Versailles. Not so long after that, the ILO was stopped in the year 1945 – 1946.

Later, the ILO was re-initiated as part of the United Nationals (UN) that operates on the basic human rights guarantees, including an equality of human dignity and right. Practices will need to respect humanity, whether in any circumstances be entitled to equality between gender, race, language, religion, and equality between the countries in the year 1947.

The case of Thailand, The beginning of human trafficking was claimed by many scholars that the trafficking occurred before the days of the Sukhothai Kingdom. That was just an assumption made by scholars. The clear evidences to proved that since Ayutthaya period, Thailand have the human trade existed was one of the regulations referred to the prostitutes or any person who sale himself cannot be a witness for the justice of administrative laws. Since the raise of Rama the fifth period, the country was quick developed, his majesty the king was put all affords to develop the country especially developing of utilities of the country such as roads, rail, bridges. This is lead to the import of Chinese labour as it is the

cheaper labour. The numbers of Chinese workers are continuously increased. During his majesty Rama the sixth period, the government put the law of prostitute registration and faced the problem of uncontrollable increasing numbers. The prostitutes with no registration were a larger numbers. During the recession in 1997, the problems related trafficking (especially trafficking in women and children) was as follow.

- A) Forced labour slavery, such as labours to work in the factory, Labour in the public places, Labour in the private place, including enforcing a beggar.
- B) An increase of organ trade.
- C) The commercial sexual exploitation or sexual services both Thai prostitutes and foreign prostitutes.

The current violent in trafficking in Thailand, the ones with forced labour slavery, organ trading and the enforcing beggar have less aggressive violence comparing to the ones happen with the prostitution related trafficking. A statistical data of the Royal Thai Police indicates the severity of human trafficking (women and children) in the form of prostitution continuously intensified. [1]

It can be seen that the beginning of human trafficking (Women and Children) in many countries is derives from the relocation of labour and earning. The immigration and relocation may be derived from migration voluntary or forced using either a legitimate or illegitimate channels, as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Relationship between migration, trafficking and smuggling of people into the city [2]

Current trafficking (women and children) in the form of commercial sexual services or the prostitution is a largest issue, rather than other forms. The Ministry of Health's surveys in each year since 2000 until 2012 were continuously demonstrating a high growth number of commercial sex

trafficking, although, some years it also has occasional decreased. This is one thing that can confirm that amount of human trafficking (trafficking in women and children) in the form of commercial sexual services has actually increased. The Ministry of Health (The division of venereal diseases) claims many researchers have adopted this as the basis of a survey and 55% of the areas that have ever done research and surveys were added. From this data analysis, the remarkable point is that the women who have been working as the prostitute always do it through the establishment of various facilities in the normal businesses, both with and without acknowledge of the owners of the business. These firms have no laws or regulations to support these or allow prostitution occurs.

Problems in regard to prostitution could not be solved easily since the pattern of the trade has been changed. In 1991, a fact provided by a children foundation reported that, "there are 2 million prostitutes, 80,000 of which are children" [3]. National Operation Center on Prevention and Suppression of Human Trafficking reported in 1992 that there were approximately 200,000 prostitutes, 50,000 of which were children [3]. Several studies have predicted the number to be around 700,000 – 2,000,000 prostitutes [3]. Phasuk Phongphaijit (1996) forecasted in his study about gambling, brothels, drugs, and illegal business would be about 101,719 million Baht per year [4]. Those who engage in prostitution nowadays are not only women, men have also been found to be involved in prostitution business. Some data provided from the Division of Viral Diseases, Ministry of Public Health provided a notable notice in that the majority of women sex workers work in different kinds of establishments [5]. The survey of this research has also found all establishments are illegal, according to Thailand's Prevention and Suppression of Prostitution Act, B.E. 2539 (1996) [7].

The research of trafficking (women and children) was aimed the study the forms, size, values of the human trades especially in trafficking of women and children. The result of the research will be implemented and propose to the authority stakeholders concerned to find ways to prevent and correct the problem further.

The research objectives are first, to study the style, size and value of trafficking. (Women and Children) in Thailand, then to Study the factors that affect trafficking. (Women and Children) and lastly, using as the basis for planning a government policies.

In this study, the authors conducted a study on human trafficking (women and children) in Thailand to study in cities with economic growth which is the source of trafficking. The areas of study are Chiang Mai, Bangkok, Phuket, Hat Yai, and Nakorn Ratchasima. In addition, this research also including studying the factors that affect entry into the sex trade in various locations in the following massage parlour, massage, clubs, bars, cocktail lounges, karaoke, call girl, young prostitutes, studying prostitutes, teahouses, gay bars, poll dancing prostitution, public streets, cafes, coffee shops, hotels and foreign prostitutes.

Thailand's Anti- Prostitution Law of B.E. 2539 (1996) [7] has been enforced in order to abrogate the prostitution business, at this time legal business licenses previously issued for both business owners and the women under this type of engagement were terminated.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research of Thailand and Procession of Trafficking Human Beings (Women and Children) is a combination of Qualitative research and the Quantitative research approach. Data used in the study are including primary data from the in-depth interviews with the former owner, stakeholder well-informed person, organizations that provide assistance to trafficking, a human, women and children protecting organizations. It was a survey in the target areas in order to study a real actual happened situation related to the questions of the study. For the secondary data were studied through texts articles in academic journals newspaper, related research papers, magazines, and internet documents for example. A review of the recent literatures, presentations etc. were critical analysed and described by the descriptive analysis.

To estimate the numbers and size of trafficking achieved by the direct method and indirect method, the financial based estimation (currency approach) will be determined by the people who hold money increases abnormally. As the effect of making illegal estimated indirectly estimated data level integration (Macro), which is approximately the size of a business alone. Direct estimates were done by the means of exploring and interviews. The estimated number of human trafficking in the form of prostitution in Thailand based on figures from the Ministry of Health bring additional estimates of the information in to the interview , and exploring the area in various sectors. In addition, number of consuming, the amount of spending each time they came for the service. The estimated results have a huge size and importance (Magnitude). Although, it is not 100% accurate statistical information but it can be used to engage in economic policy or demonstrated the importance of the quest. Estimation were designed to select a low numbers and a high level to avoid problems and the over estimations.

IV. FINDINGS

The study of the style, size and value of trafficking (Women and Children) in the context of the sex trade found that firms are being provided sexual services is identified as beer bar with up to 78,116 people, then karaoke with about 45,008 people, about 36,038 people in a bar, discotheques 21,234 people, and massage parlours 12,906 people, which are five most popular places to place people from trafficking. (Trafficking in Women and Children) in the context of the sex trade happened. The coffee shops have the least a number of commercial sexes with only 114 people. It is obvious that only trafficking in the context of the sex trade is about 81 percent of human trafficking occurred across the country with number of 240,000 people.

What are the reasons of increasing numbers of trafficking all over the country to be as many as 240,000 people? In fact, there are several factors that affect the numbers of women trafficking are incessant growing.

- A. Economic factors, an unemployment, a migration of labour to urban agriculture, Sex Tourism the impact of technological advances, global communication and more convenient. [1]
- B. The social and cultural factors; Social attitudes have changed over the moral less importance than materialism. A broken family is a major cause of the problem of inequality of income distribution to rural areas [6].
- C. The political and legal factors; Laws and penalties are not severe and not strong enough, negligence of duty of public officials or not taken seriously in the suppression [6]. Contradictory to the factors that noticeable is the estimated average monthly income that the prostitute from the minimum of 1,000 US Dollars (USD) up to 8,800 USD a month (1 USD = 32 Thai Baht) Comparing the income the prostitute usually earn to the salary undergraduates and muster graduates can earn per month, the prostitutes' income is obviously higher than other jobs. This became the motive to become the prostitutes. Therefore, policies or measurement of the government to tackle trafficking (women and children) should be oriented to the business five categories as mentioned above. And it should be more strict with businesses and deal with these firms in operate their business legally. The researcher does believe that these problems will be decrease.

V. DISCUSSIONS

In 2012, the total potential business value of the human trafficking activities (Women and Children) was 8,750 million U.S. dollars a year. The highest earning businesses were Thai traditional massage, beer bar, massage parlour, karaoke and the prostitutes' house respectively. The largest earning was set under the surface of Thai Traditional Massage about 2,700 million USD, representing almost a quarter of the total (32 percentages). The second large amount of annual income is the beer bars with average income of 1,650 million USD. Third, the massage parlours make about 1,360 million USD and fourth are the Karaoke bar or business earns about 950 million USD. The fifth was the entrepreneurs who totally made 463 million USD from prostitute related trafficking firms. These five trafficking businesses groups mentioned above have made a large number of earning. Comparing with other types of services, these five groups together will be able to be 84 percentages of other business in their overall earning. Thai traditional massage service is the most interesting business as it can make load of money. It should be checked and controlled since the studies have demonstrated that the trafficking, the prostitution type is usually hid in the surface of Thai traditional massaging. This is lead to ruining image of Thai traditional massage services that affect to a negative

industry plan. A long-term planning, the government policy has for encouraging Thai traditional massage into a commercial operated business with the international benchmarks, the hidden prostitute activity will be main obstacle obviously.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

In responding to the findings of this research, there were some recommendations to be highlighted. Policy options towards prostitution in Thailand should be laid out within the following two approaches.

The study found that trafficking (women and children) are likely expanded. Forms of trafficking in women and children have been changed since the adaptation to follow the dynamics of the environment, economy, culture, society, politics and law. The main reason of the increased growth of these businesses is because of the unavoidable fact its make a lot of money. They are worth to invest. Along with the government has too loosed penalties compared to the benefits of high rate returns that is noticeably higher than the value of the penalties you having. The government, therefore, realized and see the importance of such issues. Law enforcement with additional penalties has become the interesting point need to be clear throughout a day. Hence, the fear of the offender or the thought to act by law enforcement might scare person not to do the wrong things while, the penalties should be divided into the following two cases.

The first case study, the victims, age between 15-18 years old, or younger, twice strong penalty. And it is important that if the government officers break the rules, he or she must punished as same as others. These groups of people, they are always looking for the benefits by using their work positions to be benefit to the case that you are in. [1]

The Second case: if the trafficking was done under the agreement between two sides. The misdemeanours must be guilty with the stronger penalty than the current one but might lighter that the first cased mention above in order to stop spreading this type of business. The victim that a woman and child prostitution will be healed, the government must assist in restoring the body and mind. The Education skills need to be developed. And to be able to pursue a career feed them in the future.

VII. LIMITATION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Limitation of this paper concerns a question of whether the sample is a representative of the total population. Further research may study the level of risks and dangers from doing prostitutes and illegal business. The use of different sample sites for collecting data would add some value information to this ongoing problem. Additional studies should be focused on an exploratory research on what truly helps to understand the risks and dangers of doing illegal business, especially in respect to prostitute customers, as well as illegal business patrons.

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